
Analysis of Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as Mediation

Dede Solihin¹, Imbron², Nandang Hidayat³

^{1,2} University of Pamulang, South Tangerang Indonesia

³ University of Pakuan, Bogor Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the factors that influence customer loyalty with customer satisfaction as a mediator at PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. The method used is a casuality design. The population in this study were all customers of PT. Alfa Indah Abadi with a sample size of 100 respondents. Data collection techniques using questionnaires and data analysis methods using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The results of the study indicate that product quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. Brand image has an effect on customer satisfaction but is not significant. Product quality has no effect on customer loyalty. Brand image has no effect on customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction has a significant effect on customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction is indirectly able to be a mediating variable between product quality and brand image on customer loyalty.

KEYWORDS: Product Quality, Brand Image, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of the sandal fashion industry shows interesting symptoms to study. From year to year the demand for shoes continues to increase. Seeing the increasing demand from the community and the still small number of sandal manufacturers, many entrepreneurs see this phenomenon as a promising business opportunity, so that now many sandal industries have emerged. In the tight competition in fashion, especially shoes, manufacturers are required to offer their own advantages in order to provide satisfaction to their customers, which is expected that consumers remain loyal to the company and increase their purchases.

PT. Alfa Indah Abadi is one of the sandal manufacturers that sells its products online through the marketplace application, namely Shopee. which tries to offer product quality with a good brand image to consumers. In an effort to increase customer satisfaction, PT. Alfa Indah Abadi continues to strive to improve product quality and brand image. By trying to improve product quality and brand image, it is hoped that the customer loyalty desired by the company can be created. However, in reality, seen from the researcher's temporary observations, consumers of PT. Alfa Indah Abadi sandal products show less loyalty in their purchases. even though PT. Alfa Indah Abadi has offered advantages in terms of quality and good brand image. Related to this problem, rezeach needs to be conducted in an effort to solve problems related to customer loyalty.

Customer loyalty is a crucial factor for companies in increasing sales volume and this can be achieved if a customer makes continuous purchases. This can be done if the customer is loyal. And also loyal customers not only buy products repeatedly but will also share experiences in using products and invite other customers to consume products from the company, (Daniswara & Rahardjo, 2023). From the results of research conducted by Albari & Kartikasari (2019) it shows that customer loyalty plays a role in the survival of the company from time to time.

Customer satisfaction is the level of a person's feelings after comparing the performance or results they feel compared to their expectations (Panjaitan, 2020). Indicators of customer satisfaction according to Tjijtono in (Indrasari, 2019) are the conformity of expectations, interest in revisiting and availability of recommendations. By successfully providing satisfaction to customers, customers can make repeat purchases so that they can be called customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction is a key factor that can influence customer loyalty. When customers are satisfied with the products or services provided, they tend to repurchase the product or use the service in the future. Satisfaction is created when customer expectations are met or even exceeded, both in terms of product quality, price, service, and overall experience, (Kristianto & Wahyudi, 2019).

Product quality is a good starting point for creating a positive image and maintaining long-term customer loyalty (Azizan & Yusr, 2019). The higher the quality level of a product, the higher the level of satisfaction felt by consumers, with the high satisfaction felt by consumers, consumers will recommend the product to others (Biscaia, et al, 2017). In the business offered is a product, either goods or services, which will then be transacted, namely the buyer gets the goods sought while the seller gets money as a

Analysis of Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as Mediation

form of profit. Therefore, product quality must be considered carefully because it will determine whether consumers will be satisfied with the products they get, (Cuong, 2020).

Brand image is a set of consumer beliefs about a particular brand, such as associations embedded in consumer memory (Kotler and Armstrong, 2020). Brand image reflects the feelings that consumers and businesses have about the entire organization and individual products or product lines. Brand image can be called the face of a brand that must be maintained so that it always has a positive impression. There are indicators that form a brand image according to Budiastari (2018), namely the superiority of brand associations, the strength of brand associations and the uniqueness of brand associations.

Based on previous research conducted by Hazhbar al-Sadati et al., (2016); Khoironi et al, (2018); Mohamed Shoffian et al., (2021); Rizki & Prabowo (2022) concluded that product quality has a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty. Research conducted by Wilson (2019) has research results that product quality has a positive impact on customer loyalty, but not significantly. The results of research by Dam & Dam (2021); Desyana & Basri, (2019) and Margaretha & Rodhiah (2021) stated that there is a positive and significant influence of brand image on customer loyalty and customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, another study, conducted by Halim et al., (2014), stated that the results of the study showed a positive but not significant influence on customer loyalty. With the research that has been described above, it can be seen that brand image is a factor that needs to be considered by companies in increasing customer loyalty.

Although many studies have shown that product quality and brand image have a significant impact on customer loyalty, the role of customer satisfaction as a mediating variable in this relationship is not fully understood. Several previous studies have focused on the direct relationship between product quality or brand image and loyalty, but few have examined how customer satisfaction can act as a mediator in this relationship. This study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the effects of product quality and brand image on customer loyalty, with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable. By understanding the role of satisfaction in this relationship, companies can be more effective in formulating strategies that can increase their customer loyalty sustainably.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Improving product quality can have a positive impact on customer perception and can help companies achieve their business goals. Therefore, companies need to invest in developing and maintaining high product quality. The relationship between product quality and customer satisfaction can be proven from research conducted by Setiawan & Rastini (2021) which confirmed that there is a positive and significant relationship between product quality and customer satisfaction. Which proves that better product quality will have an impact on better customer satisfaction as well. Another study conducted by Wantara & Tambrin (2019) showed that product quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. And in another study conducted by Xhema et al. (2018) confirmed that there is a positive and significant relationship between product quality and customer satisfaction.

H1: Product Quality has a positive effect on Customer Satisfaction

Brands function as differentiators between one product and another. This makes it easier for people to remember products on the market. Consumers are able to evaluate similar products with different brands based on experience. Mohammed & Rashid (2018) stated that brand image has a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction. In addition, research conducted by Sharma (2020) obtained results that brand image is positively and significantly related to customer satisfaction. In addition, research conducted by Cuong (2020) found positive and significant results between brand image and customer satisfaction.

H2: Brand Image has a positive effect on Customer Satisfaction

Products are everything that can be offered in the market to get attention, demand, use or consumption that can meet consumer needs. From research conducted by Khoironi et al, (2018) obtained results that product quality has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. In other research conducted by Lise & Sitio (2020) in the study it was proven that there is a positive and significant relationship between product quality and customer loyalty. Furthermore, in research conducted by Xhema et al. (2018) where the study confirmed that product quality has a positive and significant impact on customer loyalty.

H3: Product Quality has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty

The relationship between brand image and customer loyalty is influenced by a satisfying product user experience. Consumers who are loyal to a brand will continue to make repeat purchases because they already trust and feel satisfied so that consumers are not easily tempted by promotions from competitors and there is a willingness to recommend the brand to others. Research conducted by Durmaz (2018), which resulted in brand image having a significant impact on customer loyalty directly. Furthermore, research conducted by Wilson (2020) confirmed that the relationship between brand image and customer loyalty has a positive and significant relationship. In another study conducted by Desyana & Basri (2019) confirmed that the relationship between brand image and customer loyalty has a positive and significant impact directly.

H4: Brand Image has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty

Analysis of Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as Mediation

Customer-oriented companies will always prioritize customer satisfaction with the products and services offered. Customers will feel satisfied if their needs, expectations, and desires can be met. Research conducted by Durmaz (2018), which resulted in customer satisfaction significantly impacting customer loyalty directly. Furthermore, Wilson (2020) confirmed that the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty has a positive and significant relationship. In another study conducted by Desyana & Basri (2019) confirmed that the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty has a positive and significant impact directly.

H5: Customer Satisfaction has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty

In a study conducted by Albari & Kartikasari (2020), it was found that customer satisfaction is a mediating variable between product quality and customer loyalty. Which means that increasing customer loyalty can occur when the quality of the product produced is good and the quality of the product will make customers feel satisfied. Research conducted by Abbas et al., (2021) the results of the study were that there was a significant and positive relationship between brand image and customer loyalty with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable for both variables.

H6: Product Quality has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction

H7: Brand Image has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction

Figure. 1 Theoretical Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

his study is an explanatory study, namely a study on the relationship between research variables by testing previously made hypotheses (Ghozali, 2018), namely the relationship between product quality and brand image on customer loyalty with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable. The population in this study were all customers who purchased PT. Alfa Indah Abadi products. The sampling method used in this study was the non-probability sampling technique with accidental sampling, namely the sampling technique based on coincidence, anyone who was met and was suitable as a data source, and had purchased PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. The number of samples was set at 100 respondents. Data was collected using the questionnaire method, namely a data collection technique carried out using a questionnaire list that had been distributed to all respondents with the aim of obtaining data on the object of research. In this study, the researcher used the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique or structural equation model. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a multivariate analysis technique used to test theories about a collection of relationships between a number of variables simultaneously.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Convergent Validity

The following are the results of validity and reliability testing of each indicator for each research variable.

Table 1. Validity and Reliability Test Results

Variable	Indicator	SLF	AVE	CR	Information
Product Quality	X1	0.564	0.65	0.85	Valid and Reliable
	X3	0.595			Valid and Reliable
	X4	0.847			Valid and Reliable
Brand Image	X6	0.456	0.76	0.77	Valid and Reliable
	X7	0.632			Valid and Reliable
	X9	0.562			Valid and Reliable

Analysis of Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as Mediation

Variable	Indicator	SLF	AVE	CR	Information
	X10	0.662			Valid and Reliable
	X111	0.711			Valid and Reliable
	Customer Satisfaction	X12	0.635	0.53	0.88
	X13	0.767			Valid and Reliable
	X14	0.573			Valid and Reliable
	Customer Loyalty	X15	0.534	0.62	0.82
	X16	0.595			Valid and Reliable

For the Product Quality variable, there are three indicators, namely X1, X3, and X4. All of these indicators have SLF values that meet the requirements, with X1 (0.564), X3 (0.595), and X4 (0.847). The AVE for these indicators is 0.65, indicating that the variation in data explained by its latent factors is quite significant. CR reaches 0.85, indicating good reliability, so the Product Quality variable can be considered valid and reliable. In the Brand Image variable, there are five indicators: X6, X7, X9, X10, and X111. The SLF values range from 0.456 to 0.711, with X6 (0.456) slightly lower than the other indicators. However, the AVE for this variable is 0.76 and the CR is 0.77, indicating that the Brand Image variable is also valid and reliable. For the Customer Satisfaction variable, indicators X12, X13, and X14 have SLF between 0.573 and 0.767. The AVE value of 0.53 indicates that although it still meets the minimum limit, there is room for improvement in the variation of data explained by these indicators. The CR for this variable is 0.88, indicating very good reliability. Finally, for the Customer Loyalty variable, indicators X15 and X16 have SLF values ranging from 0.534 to 0.595. The AVE for this variable is 0.62 and the CR reaches 0.82, indicating that Customer Loyalty is also valid and reliable. Overall, all variables tested in this study can be said to be valid and reliable, because they meet the standards set for SLF, AVE, and CR.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis Test

The next analysis is the Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis in Full Model which is intended to test the model and hypothesis developed in this study. Model testing in Structural Equation Model is carried out with two tests, namely the model suitability test (Goodness - of-Fit Test) and the causality significance test through the regression coefficient test.

Figure 2 Structural Model

Table 2. Evaluation of Goodness-of-Fit Index Criteria

Goodness-of-fit index	Cut-off value	Data Results	Evaluation
χ^2 ($X\eta_1 - \sigma\theta\alpha\rho\epsilon$)	$\leq 91,670$	42.762	Good Fit
Significance probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,88	Good Fit
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,00	Good Fit
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,93	Good Fit
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,97	Good Fit
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,00$	0,777	Good Fit
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	1,043	Good Fit
CFI	$\geq 0,95$	1,000	Good Fit

Analysis of Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as Mediation

The results of the model feasibility test seen above show that the value is within the expected range. The model evaluation shows that out of 8 criteria, it has met the recommended critical value. Therefore, referring to the principle of parsimony, the model as a whole can be said to be in accordance with the data and can be analyzed further.

Regression Weigh

Statistical tests of the relationship between variables are the basis for the research hypothesis that has been proposed. Statistical tests of the processing results with SEM are carried out by looking at the level of significance of the relationship between variables as seen through the C.R value and the Probability value of each relationship between variables.

Table 3 Regression Weight

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Customer Satisfaction	<---	Product Quality	0.522	0.187	2.791	0.005
Customer Satisfaction	<---	Brand Image	0.329	0.289	1.139	0.255
Customer Loyalty	<---	Product Quality	0.096	0.158	0.608	0.543
Customer Loyalty	<---	Customer Satisfaction	0.892	0.175	5.105	***
Customer Loyalty	<---	Brand Image	0.111	0.202	0.551	0.582

In table 3 above, not all variables have significant regression weight estimate values with a critical ratio value of ≥ 1.96 with a probability of ≤ 0.05 , so that not all alternative hypotheses are accepted. Product Quality towards Customer Satisfaction can be accepted because it has a CR value of 2.791 with a probability of 0.0005. Brand Image towards Customer Satisfaction cannot be accepted because it has a CR value of 1.139 with a probability of 0.255. Product Quality towards Customer Loyalty cannot be accepted because it has a CR value of 0.608 with a probability of 0.0543. Customer Satisfaction towards Customer Loyalty can be accepted because it has a CR value of 5.105 with a probability of 0.000 and finally Brand Image towards Customer Loyalty cannot be accepted because it has a CR value of 0.551 with a probability of 0.582.

Table 4 Direct Effect, Indirect Effect and Total Effect

Relationship	Product Quality With Customer Satisfaction	Brand Image With Customer Satisfaction	Product Quality With Customer Loyalty	Brand Image With Customer Loyalty	Customer Satisfaction With Customer Loyalty
Direct Effect	0,552	0,329	0,096	0,111	0,892
Indirect Effect	0,000	0,000	0,466	0,293	0,000
Total Effect	0,522	0,329	0,562	0,405	0,892

Based on the table above, it can be seen that there is a positive direct effect of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction of 0.522, a positive direct effect of Brand Image on Customer Satisfaction of 0.329, a positive direct effect of Product Quality on Customer Loyalty of 0.096, a positive direct effect of Brand Image on Customer Loyalty of 0.111, a positive direct effect of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty of 0.000. From these results, the Product Quality variable has the greatest direct effect on Customer Satisfaction while the Customer Satisfaction variable has the greatest direct effect on Customer Loyalty.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Product Quality on Consumer Satisfaction

Based on the first hypothesis, it indicates that Product Quality has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction at PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. It can be seen from the results of data processing which shows a P value of $0.005 < 0.05$ and C.R of $2.791 > 1.96$. Thus, product quality can be considered a factor that significantly influences customer satisfaction in this company. This study supports the results of Chandra's (2019) study that the perception of product quality has a direct effect on the level of satisfaction. The effect of product quality perception on satisfaction is positive, meaning that when product quality is perceived as high, it causes higher satisfaction, and when product quality is perceived as low, it causes lower satisfaction.

The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Satisfaction

Based on the second hypothesis, it indicates that Brand Image has an effect but is not significant on Customer Satisfaction of PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. This indicates that a good and well-known brand does not necessarily guarantee customer satisfaction. This result can be seen from the data obtained where P is $0.194 > 0.05$ and C.R is $1.139 > 1.96$. Although a positive brand image can build initial trust, it does not always guarantee that customers will be satisfied with the products or services provided. Customer satisfaction is more influenced by product quality, direct experience with the service, and how well the product meets their needs or expectations, which may not always be in line with the brand image. The results of this study are not in line with the research of Mohammed & Rashid (2018); Sharma, (2020) and Cuong (2020) where there are positive and significant results between brand image and satisfaction.

Analysis of Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as Mediation

The Influence of Product Quality on Consumer Loyalty

Based on the third hypothesis, it indicates that Product Quality does not affect Customer Loyalty of PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. This indicates that product quality does not guarantee that customers will repurchase PT. Alfa Indah Abadi products. This result can be seen from the data obtained where P is $0.543 > 0.05$ and $C.R$ is $0.608 < 1.96$. This means that the higher the product quality cannot cause stronger brand loyalty. This study is not in line with the results of Hariedhi's research (2017) that product quality has a positive and significant influence in influencing brand loyalty.

The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty

Based on the fourth hypothesis, it indicates that Brand Image does not affect Customer Loyalty. This indicates that brand image cannot guarantee customer loyalty of PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. This can be seen from the data obtained where the P value is 0.582 and $C.R$ is 0.551 . These results are not in line with research by Durmaz (2018); Wilson (2020); and Desyana & Basri (2019) in the study confirmed that the relationship between brand image and customer loyalty has a positive and significant impact directly.

The Influence of Consumer Satisfaction on Consumer Loyalty

Based on the fifth hypothesis, it indicates that Customer Satisfaction has an effect on Customer Loyalty. This result can be seen from the data acquisition where the P value is $0.000 < 0.05$ and $C.R$ is $5.105 > 1.96$. This means that the higher the customer satisfaction, the higher the customer loyalty or the lower the customer satisfaction, the lower the customer loyalty. So the seventh hypothesis in this study has been proven true. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Durmaz (2018), where the study resulted in brand image having a significant impact on customer loyalty directly. The study was conducted in the city of Bungol, Turkey with 286 respondents. Furthermore, the relationship between brand image and loyalty is proven by research conducted by Nicholas Wilson (2020), where the research was conducted at the Garuda Indonesia airline company. And confirms that the relationship between brand image and customer loyalty has a positive and significant relationship. In another study conducted by Desyana and Basri (2019), on customers of PT. Altindo Mulya. And the research confirms that the relationship between brand image and customer loyalty has a direct positive and significant impact.

The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty with Consumer Satisfaction

Based on the results of statistical tests, it was found that customer satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of product quality and brand image on customer loyalty. This means that customer satisfaction functions as an intermediary that explains how product quality and brand image affect customer loyalty. In this context, product quality and brand image can affect customer satisfaction, which in turn will increase customer loyalty. These results emphasize the importance of companies to focus not only on improving product quality and brand image, but also on customer experience and satisfaction, because the satisfaction achieved will increase the likelihood of long-term loyalty. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Albari and Atika Kartikasari (2020) who obtained results if customer satisfaction is a mediating variable between product quality and customer loyalty. Which means that increasing customer loyalty can occur when the quality of the product produced is good and the quality of the product will make customers feel satisfied. research conducted by Umair Abbas et al., (2021) on various brands with 300 respondents in the city of Multan. The results of the study were a significant and positive relationship between brand image and customer loyalty with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable for both variables.

V. CONCLUSIONS

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that product quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. Which means that respondents consider that good product quality will further increase customer satisfaction in purchasing PT. Alfa Indah Abadi products. Brand image has an effect on customer satisfaction but is not significant. Which means that respondents consider the brand image of PT. Alfa Indah Abadi has not fully provided satisfaction to customers. Product quality has no effect on customer loyalty. Which means that respondents consider that there is still product quality that does not meet customer needs so that customers are still hesitant to shop again at PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. Brand image has no effect on customer loyalty. Which means that respondents consider that brand image does not guarantee customers to remain loyal to shopping at PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. Customer satisfaction has a significant effect on customer loyalty. Which means that respondents consider that if customer needs are met and customers are satisfied, customers will be loyal to buying products at PT. Alfa Indah Abadi. Customer satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of product quality and brand image on customer loyalty, meaning that customer satisfaction functions as an intermediary that explains how product quality and brand image affect customer loyalty.

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Analysis of Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as Mediation

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Analysis of Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as Mediation

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